

I want to invent something. Proceed to auto-invent different fractal clocks that the models on and in my headboard in those document folders have. These fractal clocks come in different fractal shapes and fractal sizes of all variations. Proceed to apply a fractal shape and a fractal size to each clock model I have created, whether it is a time travelling clock, a timespace travelling clock, or a year space travelling clock.

Set.